

Precipitating factors of heart failure admission: Differences related to age and left ventricular ejection fraction

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Aim

To evaluate [precipitating factors](#) (PF) of exacerbation in heart failure (HF) and their relationship with age, preserved vs. reduced [left ventricular ejection fraction](#) (LVEF) and short-term prognosis.

Methods

We included and followed 2962 patients admitted with [acute HF](#) to [Internal Medicine](#) Units. Several PF were identified. Differences in PF according to preserved vs. reduced LVEF and age (patients ≥ 80 years vs. younger) were analyzed. Primary endpoints were readmission due to worsening HF and all-cause mortality at 3 months follow-up. Multivariable [Cox models](#) were conducted to identify the independent predictors of 3-months mortality and readmission.

Results

More than half of the patients were 80 years and over, 47% were women and 61% had preserved LVEF. [Atrial fibrillation](#) (AF) and [myocardial ischemia](#) were the more common cause of decompensation among octogenarians. It was more frequent to find [myocardial ischemia](#) or non-adherence to treatment as precipitants in patients with [systolic dysfunction](#). However, [respiratory infections](#), AF and poor control of blood pressure were more usual in patients with preserved LVEF compared to those with LVEF $< 50\%$.

Patients admitted for HF precipitated by [myocardial ischemia](#) had a higher risk of readmission at 3 months (HR 1.49; CI 95%: 1.12–1.99, $p = 0.006$) and the longest hospital stay (12 days). PF showed no predictive value for mortality.

Conclusion

Myocardial ischemia as a PF was an independent marker for HF readmissions at 3-months follow-up. Precipitants are different depending on the age and LVEF of patients. Their identification could improve [risk stratification](#) and prevention strategies.